

THE DYNAMICS OF OVERSPINNING PROCESS OF BLACK HOLE AND THE ROLE OF ELECTROMAGNETIC FIELD.

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Abstract

Devoted to study the dynamics of overspinning process and the effect of magnetic field on this process in order to test cosmic censorship conjecture.

Keywords

Black hole, angular momentum, Kerr–Newmann, energy

Introduction

We consider that there are two constants of motion associated with the particle, namely, conserved energy δE and conserved angular momentum δJ . We assume that these quantities are much smaller compared to that of the black hole $\delta E \ll M$, $\delta J \ll J$, so the test particle approximation holds well. When a particle enters the black hole, it adds to the mass, angular momentum, and charge of the black hole. The final mass, angular momentum, and charge of the black hole are given by $M + \delta E$, $J + \delta J$, and q , respectively. If the particle were to turn a Kerr black hole into the Kerr–Newmann naked singularity, the following condition must hold:

$$(M + \delta E)^2 < \left(\frac{J + \delta J}{M + \delta E} \right)^2 + q^2. \quad (1)$$

To deal with the near-extremal black hole with the dimensionless spin parameter close to unity, we take $J / M^2 = a / M = 1 - 2\varepsilon^2$, with $\varepsilon \ll 1$ being a small dimensionless parameter. Setting $M=1$, the allowed range of energy and angular momentum of the particle are given by

$$\left(2 - \sqrt{2} \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{q}{2\varepsilon} \right)^2} \right) \varepsilon < \delta E < \left(2 + \sqrt{2} \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{q}{2\varepsilon} \right)^2} \right) \varepsilon,$$

$$(2 + 3\varepsilon) \delta E - \frac{q^2}{2m} < \delta J < (2 + 4\varepsilon) \delta E. \quad (2)$$

The metric of the Kerr geometry in the Boyer–Lindquist coordinates is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 ds^2 = & -\left(\frac{\Delta - a^2 \sin^2 \theta}{\Sigma}\right) dt^2 - \frac{2a \sin^2 \theta (r^2 + a^2 - \Delta)}{\Sigma} dt d\varphi + \frac{\Sigma}{\Delta} dr^2 + \\
 & + \Sigma^2 d\theta^2 + \frac{(r^2 + a^2)^2 - \Delta a^2 \sin^2 \theta}{\Sigma} \sin^2 \theta d\varphi^2,
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

where M and a are the total mass and the specific angular momentum of the black hole, respectively.

We then investigate the effect of a magnetic field in the process of destroying a Kerr black hole with a charged particle. The magnetic field takes a constant value at infinity and is oriented along the axis of symmetry of the Kerr geometry. We try to understand whether or not the magnetic field can stop particles with the appropriate values of geodesic parameters from entering the black hole and thus serve as a cosmic censor.

The covariant components of the 4-vector potential of the electromagnetic field will take the form

$$A_t = -\frac{1}{2\Sigma} \{aB[\Delta(1 + \cos^2 \theta) + (r^2 - a^2) \sin^2 \theta] - 2aB(\Sigma - 2Mr)\}, \quad A_r = 0, \quad A_\theta = 0, \tag{4}$$

$$A_\varphi = \frac{1}{\Sigma} \left\{ \frac{B}{2} [\Delta a^2 (1 + \cos^2 \theta) + r^4 - a^4] - 2QMBa^3 \right\} \sin^2 \theta. \tag{5}$$

We analyze the effective potential in order to understand the effect of magnetic field on the process of destroying a black hole. We would like to be sure that the particle with the energy and angular momentum in the appropriate range as described in the earlier will start from an infinity and fall toward the black hole without encountering any turning point. The effective potential for radial motion can be given as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_{eff} = & -\frac{1}{2r^2} \left[\left(r^2 + a^2 + \frac{2Ma^2}{r} \right) \left(\delta E^2 - \frac{\beta^2}{4M^2} \Delta \right) - \left(1 - \frac{2M}{r} \right) \delta J^2 \right. \\
 & \left. - \frac{4Ma\delta E \delta J}{r} - \Delta \left(1 - \frac{\beta \delta J}{M} \right) \right],
 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Fig. 1. The dependence of the effective potential at the maximum point r_{\max} near the extremal rotating black hole placed in a magnetic field on the parametrization parameter b for both the negative $\beta < 0$ and positive $\beta > 0$ cases for the different values of magnetic parameter β

The dependence of the effective potential near the extremal rotating black hole placed in a magnetic field on the parametrization parameter for both the negative and positive magnetic parameter β has been shown. As we can see from Fig. 1, b_{cr} tends to decrease as we increase the magnitude of parameter β . At a certain critical value of β , we have $b_{cr} = 3$. Beyond this value, it is not possible for the charged particle to enter the black hole, and the test magnetic field serves as a cosmic censor.

Fig. 2. Radial dependence of the effective potential on the radial motion of the charged particle moving around the nearextremal rotating black hole immersed in a magnetic field for the different values of magnetic parameter β

The effective potential for the radial potential is plotted in Fig. 2. When the magnetic field is zero, the maximum of the effective potential is negative, thus allowing an infalling particle to enter the black hole. As we increase the magnetic field, the height of maximum tends to increase. Beyond a certain value of the magnetic field, the maximum value crosses zero and is positive. Thus, the infalling particle will turn back and will not be able to enter the black hole.

Conclusions

We have developed isofrequency pairing of non-geodesic orbits under the gravitational field of the Schwarzschild black hole immersed in external asymptotically uniform magnetic field and the dependence of the surface of region where isofrequency pairing of non-geodesic orbits occur around Schwarzschild black hole from the external magnetic field has been found. As a result, a decrease in the surface of the isofrequency pairing of nongeodesic orbits as nearly (7-10) % for the maximal values of the external uniform magnetic field $B \approx 10^6 - 10^7$ Gauss has been found. The analytical expressions for the vacuum electromagnetic fields of a quintessential rotating black hole in the external asymptotically uniform magnetic field has been obtained

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